

Natural radioactivity in algae arrivals on the Canary coast and dosimetry assessment

A. Tejera *, L. Pérez-Sánchez, J. G. Guerra, A. C. Arriola-Velásquez, H. Alonso, M. A. Arnedo, J. G. Rubiano, P. Martel

Physics Department, Universidad de Las Palmas de Gran Canaria, 35017 Las Palmas de Gran Canaria, España

* Corresponding author. *E-mail address:* alicia.tejera@ulpgc.es (A Tejera).

ABSTRACT

Nowadays, the use of wild and culture harvest seaweed in food industry is a booming productive sector. In this context, a radiological characterization of five globally common seaweed species which were collected in arrivals on Gran Canaria coast has been carried out. The studied algae species were *Cymopolia barbata*, *Lobophora variegata*, *Sargassum vulgare*, *Dictyota dichotoma* and *Haliptilon virgatum*. The radionuclides analysed by alpha and gamma spectrometry were ^{238}U , ^{234}U , ^{235}U , ^{210}Po , ^{234}Th , ^{226}Ra , ^{210}Pb , ^{228}Th , ^{224}Ra , ^{40}K and ^7Be . Activity concentrations, ratios and concentration factors (CF) were determined for all samples collected. The CF in algae were higher for reactive-particle radionuclides (^{210}Po , ^{234}Th , ^{228}Th and ^{210}Pb) than for conservative ones (^{40}K and the uranium isotopes), being for ^{210}Po , ^{228}Th and ^{234}Th one or two order of magnitude higher than those recommended by the IAEA. *L. variegata*, *C. barbata* and *S. vulgare* showed a clear preference for ^{210}Pb and ^{210}Po , for uranium radioisotopes, and for ^{40}K and ^{234}Th , respectively. A dosimetry assessment due to seaweed ingestion showed considerable values of annual committed effective dose for *H. virgatum* ($605\pm 19\ \mu\text{Sv/y}$), *L. variegata* ($574\pm 17\ \mu\text{Sv/y}$) and *D. dichotoma* (540 ± 30). $\mu\text{Sv/y}$). Hence, this study suggests that an algae radiological characterization is recommended as part of the product valorising process.

Keywords: Seaweed; natural radionuclides; concentration factors; internal dose; Canary Islands.

31 1. Introduction

32 During recent years there has been increased interest in knowledge of the
33 concentration and distribution of natural radionuclides in the marine environment, not
34 only to provide useful information for monitoring environmental radioactivity but also
35 to assess the radiation risk for marine biota and seafood consumers. Likewise, the
36 transport of radionuclides associated with biological material is not only subject to
37 physical and geological movements, but also to a variety of processes such as
38 bioaccumulation (Faganeli et al., 2017; Uddin et al., 2017), passive sinking of detritus
39 (Cochran et al., 1990), food-chain transfer (Pentreath, 1988) and horizontal and vertical
40 migration of many species (Livingston, 2004).

41 Distribution of radionuclides from the ^{238}U series (^{226}Ra , ^{210}Pb and ^{210}Po) has been
42 well studied in the marine environment. ^{226}Ra tends to be mobilized in seawater
43 whereas its progeny, ^{210}Pb and ^{210}Po , tend to be accumulated by marine biota
44 (McDonald et al., 1992), even with a higher preference for accumulation of ^{210}Po
45 relative to ^{210}Pb in brown algae (Al-Masri et al., 2003; Sirelkhatim et al., 2008). In this
46 way, ^{210}Po is the primary contributor to the natural radiation dose (Mat Çatal et al.,
47 2012). Concentration factors for ^{210}Po have been established in brown algae
48 (*Sargassum*) in the northern Gulf, with values higher than recommended by the IAEA
49 (Uddin et al., 2015). These macroalgae concentrate the radionuclides, and then they can
50 be easily passed along to a higher trophic level of the marine food chain. Therefore, the
51 marine biota can be considered as a potential bioindicator of radionuclides present in its
52 surrounding marine environment (Khan and Wesley, 2016). Regarding the ability of
53 marine organisms (such as ascidians, barnacles, mussels and brown algae) to
54 biomagnify and bioaccumulate radionuclides such as ^7Be , ^{234}Th and ^{228}Ra , Ishikawa et

55 al., (2004) have also suggested their role as biological monitors of natural radionuclides
56 in the marine environment. Accordingly, this capacity of macroalgae to accumulate
57 radioisotopes makes it possible to treat them as biological indicators of pollutants in the
58 marine environment (Chakraborty et al., 2014).

59 Traditionally, seaweeds have been used for human consumption, mainly in Asia
60 (Japan, China and Korea). In recent years, an increasing interest in eating seaweeds as
61 “sea vegetables” in the west, based on their nutritional or medicinal properties has been
62 reported (Tiwari and Troy, 2015). According to the world review by FAO (2018), in
63 2016 about 31 million tonnes (fresh weight) of algae were harvested in the world
64 fundamentally for direct human consumption, this production is more than twice that of
65 2005. However, risks for the human health related to the accumulation of some potential
66 hazardous components in the seaweeds (allergens, toxins, pathogens, heavy metals, or
67 radionuclides) have to be assessed (van der Spiegel 2013).

68 In order to evaluate the risks that are associated with algae intakes, radiological
69 hazard indicators have been reported. In this context, Praveen Pole et al. (2017)
70 calculated the total dose rate of ^{210}Po in several macroalgae species located close to
71 nuclear installations on the southeast coast of India, obtaining values a few orders of
72 magnitude lower than the limits proposed for marine biota (UNSCEAR, 2008). Also, in
73 the Gulf area and the Qingdao coast of China, the radiological hazard index values for
74 the marine biota samples in a study on ^{137}Cs , ^{40}K , ^{226}Ra , ^{228}Ra and ^{238}U reported by Al-
75 Qaradawi et al. (2015) and Yang et al. (2015) were below the levels recommended by
76 the IAEA (1992 and 2014), and there is no impact on human health for seafood
77 consumers.

78 In this study, radionuclide levels in five algae species, frequently found in canary
79 coast (Gallardo et al.,2016; Guiry, 2018), collected from algae arrivals on Las Canteras
80 beach, were analysed for the first time. Alpha and gamma spectrometry techniques were
81 used to measure ^{238}U , ^{234}U , ^{235}U , ^{210}Po , ^{234}Th , ^{226}Ra , ^{210}Pb , ^{228}Th , ^{224}Ra , ^{40}K and ^7Be
82 activity concentrations. In order to establish a radiological characterization of algae and
83 explore their use as surrounding environmental tracers, concentration factors and the
84 ratios between the uranium series and uranium/thorium series were determined, and
85 principal component analysis was done. Finally, an assessment of doses due to intakes
86 of radionuclides accumulated by algae was made.

87

88 **2. Study region**

89 The Canary Islands are located in the northeastern part of the central Atlantic Ocean,
90 southwest of Spain, northwest of the African continent (Fig. 1a). Gran Canaria (Fig. 1b)
91 is a volcanic island located in the middle of the one of the largest navigation corridors,
92 with a high traffic of ships that carry all kinds of substance (Sá et al, 2016). Las
93 Canteras beach (Fig. 1c) is one of the most important urban beaches in Spain situated in
94 the capital city of the island (Las Palmas de Gran Canaria).

95 Las Canteras beach has around 3 km of coast and about 60% of it is protected by the
96 presence of a sedimentary bar in the middle of the water, which emerges during low
97 tide. This bar leads to much smaller waves effect in the northern and central archs than
98 southern arch (Fig. 1c), where the sedimentary bar is not present (Medina Santamaría et
99 al., 2006). This beach morphodynamics, as well as the existence of a wide subtidal
100 platform favour the large accumulation of algae on the shores of the beaches, which

101 thrown by the sea after being released naturally from the rocky or sandy substrate (this
102 event is known as arrivals).

103 These arrivals of seaweed on Las Canteras beach are natural phenomena generally
104 caused by strong waves and storms in the coastal zone. The amount of algae biomass
105 that arrives on the coast of Gran Canaria depends on the strength of the incident waves,
106 the vegetation covers of the affected area at that time of year, and the local
107 oceanographic conditions like currents or tides. Occasionally, the type of swell that
108 produces the arrivals is due to strong storms generated in the North Atlantic that evolve
109 in the proximity of the Canary Archipelago especially in November and March, which
110 even can bring algae from far away (Portillo Hahnefeld, 2008).

111 In this work, five of the most common algae found in this arrivals were collected
112 (*Cymopolia barbata*, *Lobophora variegata*, *Sargassum vulgare*, *Dictyota dichotoma*
113 and *Halimtilon virgatum*). *C. barbata* (Chlorophyta group) is frequent in shallow
114 intertidal tide pools and in the subsoil sand or rock bottom, forming extensive prairies
115 between the bar and the shore of the beach (Espino et al., 2007). *L. variegata*
116 (Phaeophyceae group) is also very common from the intertidal zone to about 30 m deep.
117 It is found on rocky substrate (Espino et al., 2007). *S. vulgare* (Phaeophyceae group)
118 has its natural habitat in firm substrates in the shallow sublittoral zone and arrives on the
119 beach because of strong periods of swell with a west component. Due to their buoyancy
120 capacity, these types of algae reach the coast of the Canary Island Archipelago driven
121 by waves coming from the strong storms in southeastern North America (Espino et al.,
122 2007; Portillo Hahnefeld, 2008). *D. dichotoma* (Phaeophyceae group) is frequently
123 found on the walls of intertidal tide pools and is one of the more abundant species in the
124 Canary Islands (Espino et al., 2007). *H. virgatum* (Rhodophyta group) is found in areas
125 between 0 and 2 m, in tide pools and on intertidal platforms, which emerge during low

126 tide (Espino et al., 2007). Finally, these algae are also found in other place as Europe,
127 America, Atlantic, Caribbean, Pacific and Indian Ocean Islands (Guiry, 2018).

128

129 **3. Materials and methods**

130 *3.1. Sampling and sample preparation*

131 Algae were collected along Las Canteras beach in the intertidal area at low tide for a
132 period of 6 months, from January to June 2017. Algae were washed thoroughly with
133 seawater in situ to remove extraneous sand and debris trapped in them. Algae were
134 placed in polyethylene containers and brought to the laboratory, where they were
135 immediately oven-dried at 80 °C for 24 h, crushed in a mortar and sieved through 1-mm
136 mesh. Samples were weighed before (fresh weight, FW) and after drying (dry weight,
137 DW). The homogenized samples were deposited into PVC trunk-conical containers and
138 sealed with aluminium strips to minimize radon leakage in gamma spectroscopy
139 analyses.

140 An aliquot of about 0.5 g of each homogenized sample, previously prepared, was
141 reserved to determine ^{234}U , ^{235}U , ^{238}U and ^{210}Po radionuclides by alpha spectrometry.
142 Algae samples were weighed and spiked with a known amount of ^{209}Po and ^{232}U as
143 tracers. Then they were digested in Savillex Teflon vials in an oven at 80 °C for 48 h
144 (Hierro et al., 2012). When the solutions were totally digested, the dry residue was
145 redissolved in 8 M nitric acid. For isolation of the radionuclides of Po and U, a
146 sequential radiochemical method based on an extraction technique with tributyl
147 phosphate (TBP) was applied (Blasco et al., 2016; Bolívar et al., 2000). In this method,
148 once the radionuclides are isolated and purified, Po isotopes are spontaneously plated

149 onto silver discs overnight at room temperature while U isotopes are electrodeposited
150 onto stainless steel discs.

151 *3.2. Gamma and alpha spectrometric analysis*

152 Radionuclides of the ^{238}U series (^{234}Th , ^{226}Ra and ^{210}Pb) and ^{232}Th series (^{228}Ra ,
153 ^{228}Th and ^{224}Ra), and non-series radionuclides like ^{40}K and ^7Be , were determined by
154 gamma spectrometry. This technique also allows detection of anthropogenic gamma-
155 emitter radionuclides such as ^{137}Cs , ^{241}Am or ^{131}I . For each sample, two gamma
156 measurements were made. A first gamma measurement was made (within 3 and 8 after
157 collection) in order to obtain the activity of short-lived radioisotopes such as ^7Be , ^{224}Ra
158 and ^{234}Th . Subsequently, the samples were stored for at least 28 days before the second
159 gamma count to allow secular equilibrium between ^{226}Ra and ^{222}Rn (Arnedo et al.,
160 2013, 2017).

161 Gamma spectrometric measurements were performed with a CANBERRA Extended
162 Range (XtRa) Germanium spectrometer, model GX3518. This detector has 38% relative
163 efficiency to a $3'' \times 3''$ area, and nominal FWHM of 0.875 keV at 122 keV and 1.8 KeV
164 at 1.33 MeV, and it works coupled to a CANBERRA DSA-1000 multichannel analyser.
165 Efficiency calibration of the system is carried out using the CANBERRA LabSOCS
166 package based on the Monte Carlo method (Arnedo et al., 2017; G. Guerra et al., 2015 ,
167 2017). Calibration was verified using reference standards for IAEA RGK-1, RGU-1 and
168 RGTh-1. Energy calibration was performed using $^{155}\text{Eu}/^{22}\text{Na}$ (CANBERRA
169 ISOXSRCE, 7F06-9/10138 series) and confirmed using the 1460.8 keV line of ^{40}K
170 (IAEA RGK-1) (Arnedo et al., 2017).

171 For each sample, the activity concentrations of ^{234}Th , ^{226}Ra , ^{210}Pb , ^{228}Ra , ^{228}Th ,
172 ^{224}Ra , ^{40}K , ^7Be and ^{137}Cs were obtained. ^{234}Th was measured through its peak of 63.3

173 keV. ^{226}Ra was determined from ^{214}Pb using the 351.9 keV emission line. ^{210}Pb was
174 directly determined using the 46.5 keV emission line. ^{228}Ra was determined from ^{228}Ac
175 by the 911.2 keV emission line. Both ^{224}Ra and ^{228}Th were measured from ^{212}Pb by the
176 238.6 keV emission line (for the above-mentioned first and second gamma
177 measurement respectively). ^{40}K , ^7Be and ^{137}Cs were directly measured, using 1460.8
178 keV, 477.6 keV and 661.8 keV emission lines, respectively. The counting time for each
179 sample was around 86,700 s. Moreover, due decay corrections were performed so that
180 ^{224}Ra and ^{234}Th activity concentrations are referred to the collection date.

181 Measurement of alpha radionuclides was performed by ion-implanted silicon
182 detector (PIPS) α -spectrometers (CANBERRA Model PD-450.18 AM) with a 450 mm²
183 active area. The counting efficiencies of the detectors were between 21% and 25%. The
184 samples were generally measured about 5 mm from the detector and for 345,600 s, in
185 order to get appropriate minimum detectable activities (MDA) of 0.1 mBq/L (U) and
186 0.4 mBq/L (Po) (Montaña et al., 2013). For each sample, the activity concentrations of
187 ^{238}U , ^{235}U , ^{234}U and ^{210}Po were obtained by this technique.

188 Finally, regarding gamma and alpha spectrometry quality assurance, measurements by
189 means of both techniques of reference materials samples with very similar
190 characteristics to those measured in this work (organic matrix) were performed in our
191 laboratory. These reference materials were the IAEA 447 and IAEA 446 which are
192 moss and algae samples respectively. A good accordance was observed among the
193 measuring results and the reference values, confirmed by standard accuracy and
194 precision tests used in IAEA proficiency tests (Shakhashiro et al., 2012; Osvath et al.,
195 2016). Besides, the Canberra ISOCS/LabSOCS, used for gamma spectrometry analyses
196 allows efficiency calibration for a wide range of both measuring geometries (Bronson,
197 2003) and sample materials including marine biota (Yang et al., 2015).

198

199 **4. Results and discussion**

200 *4.1. Radionuclide concentration*

201 Activity concentrations of the natural radionuclides of the different algae are shown
202 in Table 1. Maximum activity concentrations for ^{238}U and ^{234}U were found for the green
203 alga, *C. barbata*, with mean values of 21.0 ± 1.7 and 29 ± 2 Bq/kg, respectively. The
204 rest of the algae, both brown and red, showed similar means, 11.6 ± 1.2 and 11.7 ± 1.1
205 Bq/kg, respectively, for ^{238}U and 14.2 ± 1.3 and 14.4 ± 1.3 Bq/kg, respectively, for ^{234}U .
206 The highest values of activity concentrations for ^{235}U were obtained for green algae
207 (with an average value of 2.8 ± 0.4 Bq/kg), and the lowest for the brown group ($0.8 \pm$
208 0.3 Bq/kg) according to the ^{235}U activities reported for certified reference material
209 IAEA-446 (0.41 ± 0.12 Bq/kg), composed of brown seaweed from the Baltic Sea (Pham
210 et al., 2014).

211 The high levels of ^{234}U and ^{238}U radioisotopes for green algae found in this work
212 contrast the results given by Burger et al. (2006) and Sakamoto et al. (2008) for algae in
213 the Pacific Ocean, reporting highest activities of both uranium radioisotopes for brown
214 algae and lowest for green algae (Table 2). They explained this result by the adsorptive
215 capacity of the alginic acid present in the cell walls of brown algae. However, the
216 opposite behaviour evidenced in this work could indicate a greater dependence on other
217 factors, such as the different biogeochemical and oceanographic properties of each
218 ocean (Atlantic and Pacific), or because different types of green and brown algae were
219 studied in each paper.

220 The mean ^{210}Po activity concentration achieved a maximum value in the brown algae
221 group (156 ± 6 Bq/kg), the highest values being recorded for the species *L. variegata*.
222 Instead, similar values were reported for green and red groups, with averages of 116 ± 5
223 and 115 ± 4 Bq/kg, respectively (Table 1). These were significantly higher than those
224 determined by other authors (Table 2), even higher than those obtained by El Samad et
225 al. (2014) in brown algae from the coastal environmental surrounding a fertilizer plant
226 (22 Bq/kg FW compared to 30.4 Bq/kg FW obtained in this work). Variations shown
227 for different locations could be due to particulate matter dynamics in each zone, driven
228 by the scavenging of ^{210}Po (Sirelkhatim et al., 2008).

229 In Table 1, it can be seen that the species *L. variegata* and *H. virgatum* showed
230 maximum mean activity concentrations for ^{210}Pb which were significantly higher than
231 those obtained by other authors (Table 2). *C. barbata* (green algae) exhibited rather
232 lower values for this radionuclide as well as for ^{234}Th ; the latter had rather higher
233 activity concentrations for the rest of the algae, especially for *S. vulgare*. This
234 enrichment of ^{234}Th in *S. vulgare* has been related to adsorption and absorption
235 processes (Ishikawa et al., 2004).

236 The minimum activity concentration for ^{40}K was obtained in *H. virgatum* (red algae).
237 The values obtained were even lower than those found in the literature for red algae
238 (Table 2). Moreover, ^7Be was only observed for *H. virgatum*, while in the rest of the
239 algae it was not detected. ^7Be is found in the atmosphere (Rajacic et al., 2017). As
240 mentioned in section 2, *H. virgatum* is found in areas which emerge during low tide, so
241 it is exposed to interaction with the atmosphere and its components while the other
242 algae species always stay underwater. This could be the reason why only these algae
243 have selectivity of absorption for this radionuclide.

244 Finally, artificial radionuclides were not detected in any samples, so it could be used
245 as an indicator of the absence of anthropogenic radioactivity in the surrounding marine
246 environment

247 4.2. Concentration Factors

248 The values of the respective activity concentrations for these radionuclides in marine
249 water (Table 3) have been taken from typical coastal water activities given by Hosseini
250 et al. (2010, 2012). Although the exact location of the algae is not known because we
251 have worked with arrivals, some measurements were made with water samples from the
252 shore of the beach, giving similar values for activity concentrations to those referenced
253 for ^{238}U , ^{234}U , ^{235}U , ^{210}Po and ^{40}K . One can see that these values are much lower than
254 the corresponding activity concentration found for algae. In order to give an idea of the
255 accumulation trend of the radionuclides in the different species of algae, the
256 concentration factor (CF) was calculated (Table 3). This is defined by the ratio of the
257 activity concentration of the radionuclide, per unit of FW, of organism tissue to the
258 corresponding activity, per unit of volume, of the seawater. It is a quantitative indicator
259 of the relationship between the organism and its environment (Inoue et al., 2005).

260 Table 3 shows that the particle-reactive ^{210}Po , ^{234}Th , ^{210}Pb and ^{228}Th had the highest
261 CF of between 10^3 and 10^4 , accumulation being slightly lower in the green algae. On the
262 other hand, accumulation of the conservative ^{238}U , ^{234}U , ^{235}U and ^{40}K was lower, with
263 CF between 10^1 and 10^2 . The CF of ^{226}Ra and ^{224}Ra were in the order of 10^2 or 10^3 .

264 It is noteworthy that the CF obtained for ^{210}Po in all macroalgae in this study was in
265 the order of 10^4 , one order greater than the IAEA recommended value for macroalgae
266 (IAEA, 2014), and the same order as found for two *Sargassum* species along the coast
267 of Kuwait (Uddin et al., 2015) and those reported for a large number of green, brown

268 and red algae along the coast near a nuclear installation on the southeast coast of India
269 (Praveen et al., 2017). ^{210}Pb had a CF of the same order as the IAEA recommended
270 value for *C. barbata* and *S. vulgare* and one order higher than for the rest of the algae.
271 With respect to the CF for ^{234}Th and ^{228}Th , all algae presented values one or two orders
272 higher than recommended by the IAEA (10^2) for thorium. Despite this high
273 accumulation, it should be taken into account that ^{234}Th is a short-lived radionuclide (24
274 days). The accumulating power of ^{226}Ra was also higher than that recommended by the
275 IAEA (2014) for all algae species, especially for *D. dichotoma* and *H. virgatum*.
276 Different authors point out that the accumulation of metals in macroalgae is very
277 variable and is determined by the life cycle, morphology, contact surface area, growth
278 rate and specific affinity for a selected metal of a particular species (Chakraborty et al.,
279 2014; Kim et al., 2017). Values obtained for uranium radioisotopes were of the same
280 order as those recommended by the IAEA.

281 Finally, this biomagnification that algae seem to exhibit for particle-reactive (^{210}Po ,
282 ^{234}Th , ^{210}Pb and ^{228}Th) against conservative radionuclides (^{238}U , ^{234}U , ^{235}U and ^{40}K),
283 could indicate a greater affinity to concentrate in the particulate phase of seawater than
284 in the dissolved one. This fact might be due to an enrichment of the algae's habitat in
285 this particle-reactive radionuclides, which are removed from the dissolved phase by
286 scavenging and sunk in the water column with the particulate phase (such as POC, PIC
287 and PN) (Wei et al., 2011; Waples et al., 2006).

288 4.3. Uranium and thorium series ratios

289 Activity concentration ratios and their average values for the ^{238}U series ($^{234}\text{Th}/^{238}\text{U}$,
290 $^{234}\text{U}/^{238}\text{U}$, $^{226}\text{Ra}/^{238}\text{U}$, $^{210}\text{Pb}/^{226}\text{Ra}$, $^{210}\text{Po}/^{210}\text{Pb}$), ^{232}Th series ($^{224}\text{Ra}/^{228}\text{Th}$), between them

291 ($^{228}\text{Th}/^{234}\text{Th}$, $^{224}\text{Ra}/^{226}\text{Ra}$), and between the uranium series ($^{235}\text{U}/^{238}\text{U}$) for the algae
292 analysed are shown in Fig. 2 and Table 4, respectively.

293 The $^{234}\text{Th}/^{238}\text{U}$ values presented important deviations from the secular equilibrium,
294 as well as from the typical marine water ratio, mainly for brown and red algae (Fig. 2a).
295 These disequilibria were also considerable for $^{210}\text{Pb}/^{226}\text{Ra}$ (Fig. 2d) and $^{210}\text{Po}/^{210}\text{Pb}$ (Fig.
296 2e). These three ratios, used for estimating the export flux of POC, PIC and PN (Wei et
297 al., 2011), once again indicate the above-mentioned hypothesis about the possible
298 adsorption/absorption of particulate phase enriched with particle-reactive
299 radionuclides (^{234}Th , ^{210}Pb , ^{210}Po). Concretely the $^{210}\text{Po}/^{210}\text{Pb}$ ratios reflect the known
300 marine biota preference for polonium, as well as the different scavenging affinities of
301 ^{210}Po and ^{210}Pb for biogenic and lithogenic particulate matter, based on their different
302 chemical behaviour (Su et al., 2017; Theng et al., 2005; Hu et al., 2014). On the other
303 hand, the $^{226}\text{Ra}/^{238}\text{U}$ values obtained were higher than the typical ratios for marine water
304 (Fig. 2c). These measured values are closer to the common ratios for coastal water
305 where submarine discharges occur.

306 Besides that, for all the algae species (Fig. 2b), similar $^{234}\text{U}/^{238}\text{U}$ ratios were found to
307 those for the marine water, around 1.3 in algae and 1.2 in oceanic water (Boryło and
308 Skwarzec, 2014). Consequently, the algae do not seem to show selective absorption of
309 these radionuclides, such as ^{40}K , which are considered to have conservative properties
310 for marine water masses. Some researchers (Inoue et al., 2005) have suggested the use
311 of radionuclides as tracers of water masses, specifically for *S. vulgare* that travels a long
312 distance and could be an indicator of the waters from which it derives. In this sense, the
313 $^{40}\text{K}/^{238}\text{U}$ ratio was calculated for *S. vulgare*; we obtained values of 420 ± 40 and $720 \pm$
314 90 for samples BS1 and BS3, and 102 ± 14 and 122 ± 14 for BS2 and BS4. This result

315 could reflect that these arrivals have been driven by water from different zones. Also,
316 $^{235}\text{U}/^{238}\text{U}$ (Fig. 2h) in all the algae followed a behaviour similar to that of the sea water.

317 Finally, results obtained for radionuclides of the ^{232}Th series (^{228}Th and ^{224}Ra)
318 exhibited no secular equilibrium (Table 4). In order to compare activity concentrations
319 between the ^{232}Th and ^{238}U series, $^{228}\text{Th}/^{234}\text{Th}$ and $^{224}\text{Ra}/^{226}\text{Ra}$ ratios were evaluated
320 (Table 4, Fig. 2g-f). *C. barbata* and *D. dichotoma* showed $^{228}\text{Th}/^{234}\text{Th}$ ratios slightly
321 over the one for coastal marine waters. Also, in Fig. 2g, a typical $^{228}\text{Ra}/^{226}\text{Ra}$ ratio for a
322 coastal zone where discharges are common, and the marine water $^{228}\text{Ra}/^{226}\text{Ra}$ ratio,
323 were also plotted. In this figure, $^{224}\text{Ra}/^{226}\text{Ra}$ values were found between those for the
324 two ratios mentioned above. This could reflect that most algae are located in coastal
325 water enriched in ^{228}Ra and so also in its progeny, ^{228}Th and ^{224}Ra . In fact, minimum
326 $^{228}\text{Th}/^{234}\text{Th}$ and $^{224}\text{Ra}/^{226}\text{Ra}$ averages were found for *S. vulgare* (Table 4) which, as
327 indicated, may well come from another ocean water region.

328 4.3. Statistical analysis

329 A Kolmogorov–Smirnov test was conducted for each single variable (radionuclides),
330 and we do not reject the null hypothesis of normality ($p < 0.05$). The Pearson correlation
331 matrix of radionuclides was calculated and is summarized in Table 5. ^7Be was not
332 considered because only red algae had values above the detection limit. Correlation
333 coefficients were considered statistically significant when $p < 0.05$. Strong positive
334 correlations were observed between ^{234}U and ^{238}U and between ^{210}Pb and ^{210}Po while
335 strong negative correlations were found between ^{234}Th and ^{238}U and ^{234}U . The latter
336 reinforces the idea already mentioned about accumulation of ^{234}Th linked more with its
337 presence in the particulate phase than with a physiological property of algae, which
338 would imply a strong but negative correlation between ^{234}Th and ^{234}U and ^{238}U . Some

339 moderate correlations were also found, positive between ^{210}Pb and ^{226}Ra , ^{224}Ra and
340 ^{210}Po , ^{224}Ra and ^{210}Pb , and negative between ^{40}K and ^{210}Po , ^{228}Th and ^{226}Ra , ^{210}Pb and
341 ^{234}U .

342 In order to confirm the underlying pattern between the radiological variables
343 (radionuclide activity concentrations) in the different groups of algae and to help the
344 data interpretation, principal component analysis (PCA) was carried out (Thomson and
345 Emery, 2014). PCA transforms the original variables into a new set of variables
346 (principal components) which are linear combinations of the original ones, in such a
347 way that usually the first two or three principal components are able to explain most of
348 the variation of all original variables (Kohler and Luniak, 2005; Matiatos et al., 2014;
349 Tang et al., 2017). The variables taken into account for this analysis were those showing
350 significant differences between groups of algae according to a one way ANOVA
351 previously carried out. Three principal components were found to explain 92.6 % of the
352 data variability, 48.7% by PC1, 35.8% by PC2 and 8.1% by PC3, respectively. The
353 factor loadings obtained for the first four principal components are shown in Table 6,
354 and scores of observations in PC1 and PC2 were plotted using a biplot (Fig. 3).
355 Additionally, considering the cutpoints of a perpendicular from each observation to
356 different variable lines of the multivariant space of the original variables (radiological
357 variables), three clusters were detected in the biplot (Fig. 3). The clusters formed by *L.*
358 *variegata* had a clear preference for ^{210}Pb and ^{210}Po , the *C. barbata* group for uranium
359 radioisotopes, and the *S. vulgare* set for ^{40}K and ^{234}Th . Identical clusters are observed
360 when PCA is performed considering all variables used in the above Pearson correlation
361 analysis, though in a PC1-PC2 biplot representing lower variance percentage (67.2%)

362 4.4. Radiological risk assessment

363 As aforementioned, human consumption of seaweed has increased significantly over
 364 the past decade. Algae are introduced into the human diet either by direct or indirect
 365 intake through the trophic chain. Other ways of influencing human could also be
 366 considered due to seaweeds are used as, food products, animal feed ingredients, for
 367 extraction of carbohydrates, fertilizers or pharmaceutical and nutraceutical applications.
 368 Seaweeds, beside to be rich in nutrients, can accumulate several compounds such as
 369 heavy metals or radionuclides from its surrounding environment, which can be harmful
 370 when they are consumed by humans (Tiwari. and Troy, 2015). Consequently, it is
 371 important to calculate a dose of activity concentration for radioisotopes by ingestion.
 372 This dose is known as the annual committed effective dose and was calculated
 373 according to the following equation (Khan and Wesley, 2016; Kim et al., 2017):

$$374 \quad ACED = MF \times e(T) \times A \times I \quad (1)$$

375 where for each radionuclide, *ACED* is the annual committed effective dose for an
 376 individual, *MF* is a weighted factor to account for the delay between seafood catch and
 377 consumption, *e(T)* is the dose conversion (1.2, 0.69, 0.28, 3.4×10^{-3} , 4.9×10^{-2} , $4.5 \times$
 378 10^{-2} and 6.2×10^{-3} $\mu\text{Sv/Bq}$ for ^{210}Po , ^{210}Pb , ^{226}Ra , ^{234}Th , ^{234}U , ^{238}U and ^{40}K
 379 respectively; UNSCEAR, 2000, 2008, 2016), *A* is the activity concentration in Bq/kg
 380 (for this dosimetry study, FW was considered), and *I* is the annual intake rate of
 381 macroalgae (kg/y) per individual. For the calculation of *MF*, it was considered that the
 382 delay which may exist in the processing and distribution of fish products from capture
 383 to consumption is 93 days for ^{210}Po , slightly less than its half-life (138.37 days) as it is
 384 recommended by UNSCEAR (2000). If for this same radionuclide the delay time were
 385 considered lower, for example 7 days (more realistic for the case of fresh algae
 386 consumption), this factor would be increased, from the value considered of 0.6 to 1.0,
 387 and the intake dose would increase too. For ^{234}Th and ^{228}Th (with a half-life of 22.1

388 days and 1.91 years respectively), MF are 0.1 and 0.9 for 93 days, or 0.8 and 1.0 for 7
389 days. Finally, MF is considered unity for ^{210}Pb , ^{226}Ra , ^{234}U , ^{238}U and ^{40}K due to its
390 longer half-life.

391 In this work, doses were calculated (Table 7) assuming an intake of 10 kg/y FW, which
392 is slightly lower than the safe recommendations for the intake of seaweeds (i.e. 11-18
393 kg/y FW) (Tiwari. and Troy, 2015). This considered value was even lower than that for
394 Asian countries where the consumption of marine food, and more specifically algae, in
395 the diet is more common, with an intake of 11 kg/y (Kim et al., 2017). Annual effective
396 dose per adult individual considering all radionuclides involving algae ingestion ranged
397 from 126 ± 7 to 423 ± 16 $\mu\text{Sv/y}$ (for 93 days delay), or 180 ± 7 to 605 ± 19 $\mu\text{Sv/y}$ when
398 7 days delay were taking account (Table 7). So we could see that the maximum ACED
399 value was for *H. virgatum* and the minimum was for *S. vulgare*. Although, in general,
400 ^{210}Po contributes most to the dose, the effective doses of ^{210}Pb for *H. virgatum* and *L.*
401 *variegata* were also high. Finally, if we compare ACED values obtained in this work
402 with representative doses due to other seafood (68.2, 181.5 and 381.8 $\mu\text{Sv/y}$ for fish,
403 crustaceans and molluscs, respectively) (Livingstone; 2004), one can see that most algae
404 (except to *S. vulgare*) presented doses higher than doses due to fish and crustaceans, and
405 even higher than of molluscs for the case of *H. virgatum*. At last, If the 7 days delay is
406 assumed doses due to algae consumption are still higher.

407 **5. Conclusions**

408 In this study, a baseline for natural radioactivity in five globally common seaweed
409 collected in arrivals on the Canary coast was established. The radionuclide
410 accumulation power of different algae species, U and Th series ratios and internal doses
411 were also determined. Besides, since these algae are not exclusive to the study region,

412 this radiological characterization could be of more general interest, and useful for
413 valorising these marine products in the future.

414 A tendency to accumulate radionuclides by seaweed has been proven, being more
415 pronounced for reactive-particle radionuclides (^{210}Po , ^{234}Th , ^{228}Th and ^{210}Pb) than for
416 conservative ones (^{40}K and the uranium isotopes). Brown and red algae exhibited CF
417 values for particle-reactive radionuclides one or two orders higher than those
418 recommended by the IAEA (2014) for macroalgae. Also, higher values for
419 disequilibrium ratios were found for $^{234}\text{Th}/^{238}\text{U}$ and $^{210}\text{Po}/^{210}\text{Pb}$. On the other hand, the
420 PCA led to three differentiated clusters corresponding to three different algae species, *L.*
421 *variegata*, *C. barbata* and *S. vulgare*, which are characterized respectively by its
422 predilection for ^{210}Pb and ^{210}Po (the former), for uranium radioisotopes (the second) and
423 for ^{40}K and ^{234}Th (the latter).

424 Annual effective dose per adult individual reached values higher than the maximum
425 values reported for other seafood in the literature, being ^{210}Po the radionuclide which
426 most contributes to the ACED (60% - 85%). For this reason, a radiological assessment
427 should be performed before the use of these algae for human consumption.

428 Finally, the radionuclide-accumulating power of algae is useful as an indicator of the
429 surrounding radiological environment, and also as tracer of different environmental
430 processes. This ability to concentrate the natural radionuclides studied in this paper
431 could also be helpful to remediate waters contaminated with radionuclides by NORM
432 industries.

433

434 **Acknowledgement**

435 Part of this work was financed by the Spanish Nuclear Safety Council (CSN) through
436 a grant from its R&D programme for 2009.

437

438 **6. References**

439 Al-Masri, M.S., Mamish, S., Budier, Y., 2003. Radionuclides and trace metals in
440 eastern Mediterranean Sea algae. *J. Environ. Radioact.* 67, 157–168.
441 [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0265-931X\(02\)00177-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0265-931X(02)00177-7).

442 Al-Qaradawi, I., Abdel-Moati, M., Al-Yafei, M.A., Al-Ansari, E., Al-Maslmani, I.,
443 Holm, E., Al-Shaikh, I., Muring, A., Pinto, P. V., Abdulmalik, D., Amir, A.,
444 Miller, M., Yigiterhan, O., Persson, B., 2015. Radioactivity levels in the marine
445 environment along the Exclusive Economic Zone (EEZ) of Qatar. *Mar. Pollut.*
446 *Bull.* 90, 323–329. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2014.10.021>.

447 Arnedo, M.A., Tejera, A., Rubiano, J.G., Alonso, H., Gil, J.M., Rodríguez, R., Martel,
448 P., 2013. Natural radioactivity measurements of beach sands in gran Canaria,
449 Canary Islands (Spain). *Radiat. Prot. Dosimetry* 156, 75–86.
450 <https://doi.org/10.1093/rpd/nct044>.

451 Arnedo, M.A., Rubiano, J.G., Alonso, H., Tejera, A., González, A., González, J., Gil,
452 J.M., Rodríguez, R., Martel, P., Bolívar, J.P., 2017. Mapping natural radioactivity
453 of soils in the eastern Canary Islands. *J. Environ. Radioact.* 166, 242–258.
454 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvrad.2016.07.010>.

455 Blasco, M., Gázquez, M.J., Pérez-Moreno, S.M., Grande, J.A., Valente, T., Santisteban,
456 M., de la Torre, M.L., Bolívar, J.P., 2016. Polonium behaviour in reservoirs
457 potentially affected by acid mine drainage (AMD) in the Iberian Pyrite Belt (SW of
458 Spain). *J. Environ. Radioact.* 152, 60–69.
459 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvrad.2015.11.008>.

460 Bolívar, J.P., Garcia-Tenorio, R., Vaca, F., 2000. Radioecological study of an estuarine
461 system located in the south of Spain. *Water Res.* 34, 2941–2950.
462 [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0043-1354\(99\)00370-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0043-1354(99)00370-X).

463 Boryło, A., Skwarzec, B., 2014. Activity disequilibrium between ^{234}U and ^{238}U isotopes
464 in natural environment. *J. Radioanal. Nucl. Chem.* 300, 719–727.
465 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10967-014-3001-9>.

466 Bronson, F., 2003. Validation of the accuracy of the LabSOCS software for
467 mathematical efficiency calibration of Ge detectors for typical laboratory samples.
468 *Journal of Radioanalytical and Nuclear Chemistry* 255 (1), 137–141.
469 <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1022248318741>

470 Burger, J., Gochfeld, M., Kosson, D.S., Powers, C.W., Jewett, S., Friendlander, B.,
471 Chenelot, H., Volz, C.D., Jeitnet, C., 2006. Radionuclides in marine macroalgae
472 from Amchitka and Kiska Islands in the Aleutians: establishing a baseline for
473 future biomonitoring. *J. Environ. Radioact.* 91, 27–40.
474 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvrad.2006.08.003>.

- 475 Chakraborty, S., Bhattacharya, T., Singh, G., Maity, J.P., 2014. Benthic macroalgae as
476 biological indicators of heavy metal pollution in the marine environments: A
477 biomonitoring approach for pollution assessment. *Ecotoxicol. Environ. Saf.* 100,
478 61–68. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoenv.2013.12.003>.
- 479 Cochran, J.K., Thomas, M.-V., Dornblaser, M.M., Hirschberg, D., Livingston, H.D.,
480 Buessler, K.O., 1990. ^{210}Pb scavenging in the North Atlantic and North Pacific
481 Oceans. *Earth Planet. Sci. Lett.* 97, 332–352. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0012-821X\(90\)90050-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/0012-821X(90)90050-8).
- 483 El Samad, O., Aoun, M., Nsouli, B., Khalaf, G., and Hamze, M., 2014. Investigation of
484 the radiological impact on the coastal environment surrounding a fertilizer plant. *J.*
485 *Environ. Radioact.* 133, 69-74. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvrad.2013.05.009>.
- 486 Espino, F., Boyra, A., Tuya F., Haroun, R., 2007. Guía visual de especies marinas de
487 Canarias, second ed. Oceanografica, Las Palmas de Gran Canaria.
- 488 Faganeli, J., Falnoga, I., Benedik, L., Jeran, Z., Klun, K., 2017. Accumulation of ^{210}Po
489 in coastal waters (Gulf of Trieste, Northern Adriatic Sea). *J. Environ. Radioact.*
490 174, 38–44. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvrad.2016.07.018>.
- 491 FAO (2018). The State of World Fisheries and Aquaculture 2018 - Meeting the
492 sustainable development goals. Rome
- 493 Gallardo, T., Bárbara, I., Afonso-Carrillo, J., Bermejo, R., Altamirano, M., Gómez
494 Garreta, A., Barceló Martí, M.C., Rull Lluch, J., Ballesteros, E., De la Rosa,
495 J., 2016. Nueva lista crítica de las algas bentónicas marinas de España. *ALGAS,*
496 *Boletín Informativo de la Sociedad Española de Ficología.*
- 497 G. Guerra, J., G. Rubiano, J., Winter, G., G. Guerra, A., Alonso, H., Arnedo, M.A.,
498 Tejera, A., Gil, J.M., Rodríguez, R., Martel, P., Bolivar, J.P., 2015. A simple
499 methodology for characterization of germanium coaxial detectors by using Monte
500 Carlo simulation and evolutionary algorithms. *J. Environ. Radioact.* 149, 8-18.
501 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvrad.2015.06.017>.
- 502 G. Guerra, J., G. Rubiano, J., Winter, G., G. Guerra, A., Alonso, H., Arnedo, M.A.,
503 Tejera, A., Martel, P., Bolivar, J.P., 2017. Computational characterization of HPGe
504 detectors usable for a wide variety of source geometries by using Monte Carlo
505 simulation and a multi-objective evolutionary algorithm. *Nucl. Instrum. Methods*
506 *Phys. Res. A* 858, 113-122. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nima.2017.02.087>.
- 507 Goddar, C.C., B.P., 2001. The Radionuclide Content of Seaweeds and Seagrass Around
508 the Coast of Oman and the United Arab Emirates. *Mar. Pollut. Bull.* 42, 1411–
509 1416. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0025-326X\(01\)00218-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0025-326X(01)00218-1).
- 510 Guiry, M.D. in Guiry, M.D. & Guiry, G.M., 2018. *AlgaeBase*. World-wide electronic
511 publication, National University of Ireland, Galway. <http://www.algaebase.org>
512 (accessed 29 November 2018).
- 513 Hierro, A., Bolivar, J.P., Vaca, F., Borrego, J., 2012. Behavior of natural radionuclides
514 in surficial sediments from an estuary impacted by acid mine discharge and
515 industrial effluents in Southwest Spain. *J. Environ. Radioact.* 110, 13–23.
516 <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvrad.2012.01.005>.

- 517 Hosseini A., Beresford NA., Brown JE., Jones DG., Phaneuf M., Thørring H.,
518 Yankovich T., 2010. Background dose-rates to reference animals and plants arising
519 from exposure to naturally occurring radionuclides in aquatic environments. *J.*
520 *Radiol. Prot.* 30, 235-264. <https://doi.org/10.1088/0952-4746/30/2/S03>.
- 521 Hosseini A., Brown JE., Gwynn JP., Dowdall M., 2012. Review of research on impacts
522 to biota of discharges of naturally occurring radionuclides in produced water to the
523 marine environment. *Sci Total Environ.* 438, 325-333.
524 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2012.08.047>.
- 525 Hu, W., Chen, M., Yang, W., Zhang, R., Qiu, Y., Zheng, M., 2014. Enhanced particle
526 scavenging in deep water of the Aleutian Basin revealed by ^{210}Po - ^{210}Pb
527 disequilibria. *J. Geophys. Res. Ocean.* 119, 3235–3248.
528 <http://doi.org/10.1002/2014JC009819>.
- 529 IAEA, 1992. Effects of Ionizing Radiation on Plants and Animals at Levels Implied by
530 Current Radiation Protection Standards, Technical Reports Series 332.
- 531 IAEA, 2014. Sediment Distribution Coefficients and Concentration Factors for Biota in
532 the Marine Environment, Technical Reports Series 422.
- 533 Inoue, M., Kofuji, H., Yamamoto, M., Komura, K., 2005. Seasonal variation of $^{228}\text{Ra}/$
534 ^{226}Ra ratio in seaweed : implications for water circulation patterns in coastal areas
535 of the Noto Peninsula, Japan. *J. Environ. Radioact.* 80, 341–355.
536 <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvrad.2004.10.007>.
- 537 Ishikawa, Y.Å., Kagaya, H., Saga, K., 2004. Biomagnification of ^7Be , ^{234}Th , and ^{228}Ra
538 in marine organisms near the northern Pacific coast of Japan. *J. Environ. Radioact.*
539 76, 103–112. <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvrad.2004.03.021>.
- 540 Khan, M.F., Wesley, S.G., 2016. Baseline concentration of Polonium-210 (^{210}Po) in
541 tuna fish. *Mar. Pollut. Bull.* 107, 379–382.
542 <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2016.03.056>.
- 543 Kim, S.H., Hong, G.H., Lee, H.M., Cho, B.E., 2017. ^{210}Po in the marine biota of Korean
544 coastal waters and the effective dose from seafood consumption. *J. Environ.*
545 *Radioact.* 174, 30–37. <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvrad.2016.11.001>.
- 546 Kohler, U., Luniak, M., 2005. Data inspection using biplots. *Stata J.* 5, 208–223.
547 <http://doi.org/10.1177/1536867X0500500206>.
- 548 Livingston, H.D., 2004. Radioactivity in the environment: Marine Radioactivity, First.
549 ed. Elsevier Ltd, Oxford.
- 550 Mat Çatal, E., Uğur, A., Özden, B., Filizok, I., 2012. ^{210}Po and ^{210}Pb variations in fish
551 species from the Aegean Sea and the contribution of ^{210}Po to the radiation dose.
552 *Mar. Pollut. Bull.* 64, 801–806. <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2012.01.016>.
- 553 Matiatos, I., Alexopoulos, A., Godelitsas, A., 2014. Multivariate statistical analysis of
554 the hydrogeochemical and isotopic composition of the groundwater resources in in
555 northeastern Peloponnesus (Greece). *Sci. Total Environ.* 476–477, 577–590.
556 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2014.01.042>.
- 557 McDonald, P., Cook, G.T., Baxter, M.S., 1992. Natural and anthropogenic radioactivity

- 558 in coastal regions of the UK. *Radiat. Prot. Dosimetry* 45, 707–710.
559 http://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-011-3686-0_35.
- 560 Medina Santamaría, R., Batón Meira, S., Cánovas Losada, V., Torres Freyermuth, A.,
561 Luque Escalona, Á., Alonso Bilbao, I., Sánchez Pérez, I., Ortega García, A.,
562 Rodríguez Valido, S., Martín García, J.A., García Jiménez, P., Santos Facundo, F.,
563 Bilbao Siero, A., López Menviel, F., Cabanillas Terán, N., Bustos León, R.,
564 Sollheim González, C., López Caballero, Y., García Fernández, Y., 2006. Estudio
565 integral de la playa de Las Canteras. *Inf. técnico para la Dir. Gen. Costas* 736.
- 566 Montaña, M., Fons, J., Corbacho, J.A., Camacho, A., Zapata-García, D., Guillén, J.,
567 Serrano, I., Tent, J., 2013. A comparative experimental study of gross alpha
568 methods in natural waters. *J. Environ. Radioact.* 118, 1–8.
569 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvrad.2012.10.009>.
- 570 Osvath, I., Tarjan, S., Pitois, A., Groening, M., Osborn, D., 2016. IAEA’s ALMERA
571 network: Supporting the quality of environmental radioactivity measurements.
572 *Appl. Radiat. Isot.* 109, 90–95. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apradiso.2015.12.062>
- 573 Outola, I., Filliben, J., Inn, K.G.W., La Rosa, J., McMahon, C.A., Peck, G.A., Twining,
574 J., Tims, S.G., Fifield, L.K., Smedley, P., Antón, M.P., Gascó, C., Povinec, P.,
575 Pham, M.K., Raaum, A., Wei, H.-J., Krijger, G.C., Bouisset, P., Litherland, A.E.,
576 Kieser, W.E., Betti, M., Aldave de las Heras, L., Hong, G.H., Holm, E., Skipperud,
577 L., Harms, A.V., Arinc, A., Youngman, M., Arnold, D., Wershofen, H., Sill, D.S.,
578 Bohrer, S., Dahlgaard, H., Croudace, I.W., Warwick, P.E., Ikaheimonen, T.K.,
579 Klemola, S., Vakulovsky, S.M., Sanchez-Cabeza, J.A. 2006. Characterization of
580 the NIST seaweed Standard Reference Material. *Appl. Radiat. Isot.* 64, 1242–1247
581 <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.apradiso.2006.02.029>.
- 582 Pham, M.K., Benmansour, M., Carvalho, F.P., Chamizo, E., Degering, D., Engeler, C.,
583 Gascó, C., Gwynn, J.P., Harms, A.V., Hrncsek, E., Ibanez, F.L., Ilchmann, C.,
584 Ikaheimonen, T., Kanisch, G., Kloster, M., Llauro, M., Mauring, A., Møller, B.,
585 Morimoto, T., Nielsen, S.P., Nies, H., Norrlid, L.D.R., Pettersson, H.B.L., Povinec,
586 P.P., Rieth, U., Samuelsson, C., Schikowski, J., Šilobriene, B.V., Smedley, P.A.,
587 Suplinska, M., Vartti, V.-P., Vasileva, E., Wong, J., Zalewska, T., Zhou, W. 2014.
588 Certified Reference Material IAEA-446 for radionuclides in Baltic. *Appl. Radiat.*
589 *Isot.* 87, 468–474. <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.apradiso.2013.11.013>.
- 590 Pentreath, J.R., 1988. Radionuclides in the aquatic environment, in: Harley, J.H.,
591 Schmidt, G.D., Silini, G. (Eds.), *Radionuclides in the Food Chain*. Springer-
592 Verlag, New York, pp. 99–119.
- 593 Portillo Hahnefeld, E., 2008. *Arribazones de algas y plantas marinas en Gran Canarias:*
594 *Características, gestión y posibles usos*, First. ed. Daute Diseño, S.L., Santa Lucía-
595 Las Palmas.
- 596 Praveen Pole, R.P., Feroz Khan, M., Godwin Wesley, S., 2017. Occurrence of ²¹⁰Po in
597 marine macroalgae inhabiting a coastal nuclear zone, southeast coast of India. *J.*
598 *Environ. Radioact.* 169–170, 122–130.
599 <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvrad.2017.01.013>.
- 600 Rajacic, M.M., Todorovic, D.J., Nikolic, J.D.K., Puzovic, J.M., 2017. The impact of the
601 Solar magnetic field on ⁷Be activity concentration in aerosols. *Appl. Radiat. Isot.*

- 602 125, 27–29. <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.apradiso.2017.04.008>.
- 603 Sá, S., Bastos-Santos, J., Araújo, H., Ferreira, M., Duro, V., Alves, F., Panta-Ferreira,
604 B., Nicolau, L., Eira, C., Vingada, J. 2016. Spatial distribution of floating marine
605 debris in offshore continental Portuguese . waters. *Mar. Pollut. Bull.* 104, 269–278.
606 <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2016.01.011>.
- 607 Sakamoto, N., Kano, N., Imaizumi, H., 2008. Determination of rare earth elements,
608 thorium and uranium in seaweed samples on the coast in Niigata Prefecture by
609 inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry. *Appl. Geochemistry* 23, 2955–
610 2960. <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.apgeochem.2008.04.011>.
- 611 Shakhashiro, A., Tarjan, S., Ceccatelli, A., Kis-Benedek, G., Betti, M., 2012. IAEA447:
612 A new certified reference material for environmental radioactivity measurements.
613 *Appl. Radiat. Isot.* 70, 1632–1643. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apradiso.2012.03.024>.
614
- 615 Sirelkhatim, D.A., Sam, A.K., Hassona, R.K., 2008. Distribution of ^{226}Ra – ^{210}Pb –
616 ^{210}Po in marine biota and surface sediments of the Red Sea , Sudan. *J. Environ.*
617 *Radioact.* 99, 1825–1828. <https://doi.org/doi:10.1016/j.jenvrad.2008.07.008>.
- 618 Strezov, A., Nonova, T., 2009. Influence of macroalgal diversity on accumulation of
619 radionuclides and heavy metals in Bulgarian Black Sea ecosystems. *J. Environ.*
620 *Radioact.* 100, 144–150. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvrad.2008.09.007>.
- 621 Su, K., Du, J., Baskaran, M., Zhang, J., 2017. ^{210}Po and ^{210}Pb disequilibrium at the PN
622 section in the East China Sea. *J. Environ. Radioact.* 174, 54–65.
623 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvrad.2016.07.031>.
- 624 Suriyanarayanan, S., Brahmanandhan, G.M., Malathi, J., Ravi Kumar, S., Masilamani,
625 V., Shahul Hameed, P., Selvasekarapandian, S., 2007. Studies on the distribution
626 of ^{210}Po and ^{210}Pb in the ecosystem of Point Calimere Coast (Palk Strait), India. *J.*
627 *Environ. Radioact.* 99, 766–771. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvrad.2007.10.003>.
- 628 Tang Y., Stewart, G., Lam, P.J., Rigaud, S., Church, T., 2017. The influence of particle
629 concentration and composition on the fractionation of ^{210}Po and ^{210}Pb along the
630 North Atlantic GEOTRACES transect GA03. *Deep-Sea Research Part I* 128, 42–
631 54. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dsr.2017.09.001>.
- 632 Theng, T. L., Abd, C., Mohamed, .R., 2005. Activities of ^{210}Po and ^{210}Pb in the water
633 column at Kuala Selangor, Malaysia. *J. Environ. Radioact.* 80, 273–286 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvrad.2004.10.004>.
634
- 635 Thomson, R.E., Emery, W.J., 2014. *Data Analysis Methods in Physical Oceanography*,
636 Third. ed, *Climate Change 2013 - The Physical Science Basis*. Elsevier B.V.,
637 Waltham. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9781107415324.004>.
- 638 Tiwari BK. and Troy DJ., 2015. *Seaweed Sustainability Food and Non-Food*
639 *Applications*, ed. Academic Press. Elsevier, London.
- 640 Uddin, S., Aba, A., Bebhehani, M., 2015. Baseline concentration of ^{210}Po and ^{210}Pb in
641 *Sargassum* from the northern Gulf. *Mar. Pollut. Bull.* 90, 330–333.
642 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2014.09.029>.

- 643 Uddin, S., Fowler, S.W., Behbehani, M., Metian, M., 2017. Po bioaccumulation and
644 trophic transfer in marine food chains in the northern Arabian Gulf. *J. Environ.*
645 *Radioact.* 174, 23–29. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvrad.2016.08.021>.
- 646 UNSCEAR, 2000. Sources and Effects of Ionizing Radiation. Report of the United
647 Nations Scientific Committee on the Effects of Atomic Radiation to the General
648 Assembly, with Scientific Annexes. United Nations, New York.
- 649 UNSCEAR, 2008. Sources and Effects of Ionizing Radiation. Report of the United
650 Nations Scientific Committee on the Effects of Atomic Radiation to the General
651 Assembly, with Scientific Annexes. United Nations, New York.
- 652 UNSCEAR, 2016. Sources, Effects and Risks of Ionizing Radiation. Report of the
653 United Nations Scientific Committee on the Effects of Atomic Radiation to the
654 General Assembly, with Scientific Annexes. United Nations, New York.
- 655 van der Spiegel M., Noordam M. Y., van der Fels-Klerx H. J., 2013. Safety of novel
656 protein sources (insects, microalgae, seaweed, duckweed, and rapeseed) and
657 legislative aspects for their application in food and feed production.
658 *Comprehensive Reviews in Food Science and Food Safety*, 12, 662–678.
659 <https://doi.org/10.1111/1541-4337.12032>.
- 660 Waples, J.T., Benitez-Nelson, C., Savoye, N., Rutgers van der Loeff, M., Baskaran, M.,
661 Gustafsson, Ö., 2006. An introduction to the application and future use of ^{234}Th in
662 aquatic systems. *Mar. Chem.* 100, 166–189.
663 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marchem.2005.10.011>.
- 664 Wei, C.L., Lin, S.Y., Sheu, D.D., Chou, W.C., Yi, M.C., Santschi, P.H., Wen, L.S.,
665 2011. Particle-reactive radionuclides (^{234}Th , ^{210}Pb , ^{210}Po) as tracers for the
666 estimation of export production in the South China Sea. *Biogeosciences* 8, 3793–
667 3808. <https://doi.org/10.5194/bg-8-3793-2011>.
- 668 Yang, B., Ha, Y., Jin, J., 2015. Assessment of radiological risk for marine biota and
669 human consumers of seafood in the coast of Qingdao, China. *Chemosphere* 135,
670 363–369. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2015.04.097>.
- 671

Fig. 1. Location of study zone; a) Canary Archipelago; b) Gran Canaria island; c) Satellite images of Las Canteras beach with its division in archs and Las Palmas port. Coordinates are in the UTM system.

Fig. 2. Ratios between $^{234}\text{Th}/^{238}\text{U}$, $^{234}\text{U}/^{238}\text{U}$, $^{226}\text{Ra}/^{238}\text{U}$, $^{210}\text{Pb}/^{226}\text{Ra}$, $^{210}\text{Po}/^{210}\text{Pb}$, $^{228}\text{Th}/^{234}\text{Th}$, $^{224}\text{Ra}/^{226}\text{Ra}$ and $^{235}\text{U}/^{238}\text{U}$ for algae samples from January 2017 to May 2017. The dashed blue line shows the radioisotope equilibrium in marine water.

Fig.3. Biplot of principal component (PC1 and PC2) scores based on observations for each algae specie (black axes). Radiological variables are plotted in blue axes. Numbers in brackets are the percentage of variance associated with each PC-axis, and ovals denote the clustering of algae samples.

Tables

Table 1

Activity concentration and their mean (Bq/kg DW) of alpha and gamma emission radionuclides for each alga sample and group. DW/FW is ratio between dry and fresh weights.

Sample	DW/FW	²³⁸ U	²³⁴ U	²³⁵ U	²¹⁰ Po	²³⁴ Th	²²⁶ Ra	²¹⁰ Pb	²²⁸ Th	²²⁴ Ra	⁴⁰ K	⁷ Be
GC1	0.146	14.9±1.2	27.5±1.9	7.0±0.8	116±5	147±12	6.1±1.7	10±6	5.3±1.3	25±3	1020±50	BDL
GC2	0.181	24.3±1.4	26.0±1.5	1.6±0.2	100±4	118±11	9.6±1.9	20±7	12.1±1.5	23±4	1010±50	BDL
GC3	0.209	22±2	33±3	1.2±0.4	129±6	89±8	2.8±1.4	13±5	8.6±1.1	9±3	550±30	BDL
GC4	0.227	23±2	28±2	1.4±0.4	119±6	100±11	18±2	25±7	14.8±1.7	8±2	1160±60	BDL
Mean		21.0±1.7	29±2	2.8±0.4	116±5	110±10	9.0±1.8	17±6	10.2±1.4	16±3	940±50	--
BL1	0.157	11.6±1.1	13.2±1.2	0.7±0.3	243±6	520±40	29±2	83±9	20.3±1.8	25±6	420±30	BDL
BL2	0.166	12.4±0.9	16.6±1.1	0.5±0.2	217±5	570±30	21±2	74±8	13.8±1.5	50±4	820±40	BDL
BL3	0.190	9.8±0.8	10.8±0.8	0.5±0.2	195±5	460±30	10.9±1.6	63±7	10.9±1.3	28±3	860±40	BDL
BL4	0.171	13.5±1.0	18.4±1.2	0.5±0.2	182±7	510±30	8.3±1.8	76±8	19.5±1.6	44±5	580±30	BDL
BL5	0.221	12.8±1.9	10.9±1.7	0.9±0.4	223±8	420±30	14±1.8	73±7	12.9±1.4	35±9	790±40	BDL
Mean		12.0±1.1	14.0±1.2	0.6±0.2	212±6	500±30	16.7±1.9	74±8	15.5±1.5	37±6	690±40	--
BS1	0.121	7.2±0.7	10.6±0.8	0.5±0.2	120±3	990±80	8.7±1.7	30±8	10.7±1.3	7±3	3040±130	BDL
BS2	0.114	12.8±1.7	15.5±1.9	1.0±0.4	118±5	860±50	17.4±1.9	35±7	5.5±1.3	19±6	1310±60	BDL
BS3	0.108	5.4±0.6	8.1±0.8	0.16±0.10	40.9±1.8	910±50	9.6±1.8	22±7	11.5±1.4	BDL	3920±170	BDL
BS4	0.152	11.3±1.2	13.9±1.3	0.4±0.2	BLD	650±40	18±3	BDL	34±3	BDL	1370±70	BDL
Mean		9.2±1.0	12.0±1.2	0.5±0.2	93±3	860±50	13±2	29±7	15.4±1.7	13±4	2410±110	--
BD1	0.317	15.6±1.1	22.5±1.5	0.9±0.2	127±6	164±11	19.0±1.5	29±5	17.4±1.2	31±4	1060±50	BDL
BD2	0.320	15±2	17±2	1.4±0.5	160±11	242±15	12.5±1.3	44±5	18.1±1.2	23±2	940±40	BDL
BD3	0.197	12.3±1.6	12.9±1.6	2.3±0.6	95±5	276±17	12.8±1.4	21±5	9.3±1.0	18±2	1510±70	BDL
Mean		14.2±1.6	17.5±1.8	1.5±0.5	127±7	227±14	14.8±1.4	31±5	15.0±1.1	24±3	1170±50	--
Brown mean		11.6±1.2	14.2±1.3	0.8±0.3	156±6	550±40	15.1±1.9	50±7	15.3±1.5	28±5	1380±60	--
RH1	0.454	11.5±0.8	13.0±0.9	0.8±0.2	130±3	1300±100	21.0±1.7	76±8	25.1±1.5	BDL	177±16	36±5
RH2	0.216	10.0±1.1	14.0±1.4	0.7±0.3	104±3	510±30	17.6±1.5	53±6	16.2±1.2	14±4	570±30	29±4
RH3	0.251	13.5±1.4	16.1±1.5	1.8±0.4	111±6	540±30	11.9±1.0	43±4	14.0±0.9	30±5	430±20	8±3
Mean		11.7±1.1	14.4±1.3	1.1±0.3	115±4	770±50	16.8±1.4	57±6	18.4±1.2	22±5	390±20	25±4

BDL: Below detection limit.

Table 2

Comparison of activity concentration in Bq/kg DF of ^{210}Po , ^{226}Ra , ^{40}K , ^{210}Po and ^{235}U in Las Canteras beach with other authors values. ^a are values in Fresh Weigh. G, B and R correspond to Green, Brown and Red, respectively.

Location	Type	^{238}U	^{234}U	^{226}Ra	^{210}Pb	^{210}Po	^{228}Th - ^{228}Ac	^{40}K	References
Las Canteras beach (Spain)	G	(14.9-24.3) 21.0	(26.0-33) 29	(2.8-18) 9.0	(10-25) 17	(100-129) 116	(5.3-14.8) 10.2	(550-1160) 940	This work
	B	(5.4-15.6) 11.6	(8.1-22.5) 14.2	(9.6-29) 15.1	(21-83) 50	(40.9-243) 156	(5.5-20.3) 15.3	(420-3920) 1380	
	R	(10.0-13.5) 11.7	(13.0-16.2) 14.4	(11.9-21.0) 16.8	(43-76) 57	(104-130) 115	(14.0-25.1) 18.4	(177-570) 390	
Point Calimere Coast	B				(13.7-95.0) 54.4	(2.8-2.9) 2.6			Suriyanarayan et al., 2007
Bulgarian Black sea	G			(3-1300)	(3-100)			(370-2500)	Strezov & Nonova, 2009
	B			(2-17)	(2-21)			(130-1990)	
	R			(2-39)	(4-41)			(124-2100)	
Arab Emirates	G			(16.5-18.3) 17.4			(4.4-61.8) 16.2	(100-4444) 1045	Goddard & Jupp, 2002
	B			(19.1-48.2) 25.6			(5.0-106) 26.2	(125-5443) 2049	
	R			(19.1-48.2) 5.1			(1.6-60.8) 15.3	(278-4373) 1643	
Syrian coast	G			<2.3	(2.3-5.6) 3.8	(7.7-15.56) 12.4		(450-1100) 850	Al-Masri et al., 2003
	B			(1.2-6.8) 3.9	(2.8-15.9) 8.1	(8.1-26.4) 19.5		(551-2260) 1523	
	R			<6	(7.8-27.5) 20.4	(19.5-27.4) 22.3		(70-1030) 402	
White Sea (NIST-SRM)	B	8.7	9.5	5.7	21.0	20.6	3.8	734	Outoula et al., 2006
Baltic Sea (IAEA-446)	B	9.3	10.5	17.0	10.9	10.9	15.0	660	Pham et al., 2014
Amchirtka and Kiska Islands	G	0.2 ^a	0.3 ^a						Burger et al., 2006
	B	(0.4-2.7) 1.2 ^a	(0.4-3.1) 1.4 ^a						
Kuwait	B				(15.3-22.0)	(22.2-25.6)			Uddin et al., 2015
Japan coast	G	(0.6-4.8)	(0.6-4.9)						Sakamoto et al., 2008
	B	(16.1-58.1)	(16.2-58.5)						
	R	(2.8-9.9)	(2.9-10.0)						

Table 3

Concentration factor (L/kg) of the different radionuclides per algae specie. BMean represents the average between the brown algae. Activity concentration of naturally occurring radionuclide in coastal marine water (Bq/L) compiled by Hoseeini et al. 2010 are also included.

Nuclide	Activity (in coastal waters)	Green		Brown			Red
		GC	BL	BS	BD	BMean	RH
²³⁸ U	0.041	1 x 10 ²	5 x 10 ¹	3 x 10 ¹	1 x 10 ²	6 x 10 ¹	9 x 10 ¹
²³⁴ U	0.047	1 x 10 ²	5 x 10 ¹	3 x 10 ¹	1 x 10 ²	6 x 10 ¹	9 x 10 ¹
²³⁵ U	0.0019	2 x 10 ²	6 x 10 ¹	3 x 10 ¹	2 x 10 ²	9 x 10 ¹	2 x 10 ²
²¹⁰ Po	0.002	1 x 10 ⁴	2 x 10 ⁴	5 x 10 ³	2 x 10 ⁴	2 x 10 ⁴	2 x 10 ⁴
²³⁴ Th	0.012	2 x 10 ³	7 x 10 ³	9 x 10 ³	5 x 10 ³	7 x 10 ³	2 x 10 ⁴
²²⁶ Ra	0.0034	5 x 10 ²	9 x 10 ²	5 x 10 ²	1 x 10 ³	8 x 10 ²	2 x 10 ³
²¹⁰ Pb	0.002	2 x 10 ³	7 x 10 ³	2 x 10 ³	5 x 10 ³	5 x 10 ³	9 x 10 ³
²²⁴ Ra(²²⁸ Ra)*	0.01	2 x 10 ²	4 x 10 ²	2 x 10 ²	6 x 10 ²	4 x 10 ²	5 x 10 ²
²²⁸ Th	0.0003	7 x 10 ³	9 x 10 ³	7 x 10 ³	1 x 10 ⁴	1 x 10 ⁴	2 x 10 ⁴
⁴⁰ K	12	1 x 10 ¹	1 x 10 ¹	2 x 10 ¹	3 x 10 ¹	2 x 10 ¹	9 x 10 ⁰

*Activity concentration of ²²⁸Ra has been considered

Table 4

Ratio between mean activity concentration of $^{234}\text{Th}/^{238}\text{U}$, $^{234}\text{U}/^{238}\text{U}$, $^{226}\text{Ra}/^{238}\text{U}$, $^{210}\text{Pb}/^{226}\text{Ra}$, $^{210}\text{Po}/^{210}\text{Pb}$, $^{224}\text{Ra}/^{228}\text{Th}$, $^{228}\text{Th}/^{234}\text{Th}$, $^{224}\text{Ra}/^{226}\text{Ra}$ and $^{235}\text{U}/^{238}\text{U}$ in green, brown and red algae of Las Canteras beach. Mean represents the average between the brown algae.

Ratio	Green		Brown			Red
	GC	BL	BS	BD	BMean	RH
$^{234}\text{Th}/^{238}\text{U}$	5.8±0.7	42±5	108±14	16±2	57±7	67±8
$^{234}\text{U}/^{238}\text{U}$	1.42±0.12	1.16±0.12	1.35±0.17	1.22±0.15	1.24±0.14	1.24±0.14
$^{226}\text{Ra}/^{238}\text{U}$	0.42±0.09	1.4±0.2	1.5±0.3	1.03±0.15	1.3±0.2	1.49±0.18
$^{210}\text{Pb}/^{226}\text{Ra}$	2.5±1.3	5.3±1.0	2.6±0.8	2.9±0.5	3.7±0.8	3.4±0.4
$^{210}\text{Po}/^{210}\text{Pb}$	8±3	2.9±0.3	3.1±0.8	4.2±0.6	3.3±0.6	2.1±0.2
$^{224}\text{Ra}/^{228}\text{Th}$	2.0±0.5	2.5±0.5	2.1±0.8	1.7±0.2	2.2±0.5	1.5±0.3
$^{228}\text{Th}/^{234}\text{Th}$	0.096±0.016	0.031±0.004	0.020±0.003	0.072±0.00	0.038±0.004	0.026±0.002
$^{224}\text{Ra}/^{226}\text{Ra}$	3±1	2.7±0.6	1.0±0.4	1.6±0.2	2.1±0.5	1.6±0.4
$^{235}\text{U}/^{238}\text{U}$	0.16±0.03	0.053±0.019	0.05±0.02	0.11±0.03	0.07±0.02	0.09±0.03

Table 5

Pearson correlation analysis between radionuclides of the algae from Las Canteras beach (correlation coefficient is shown at the bottom left diagonal and p-value cursive at the top of diagonal).

	²³⁸ U	²³⁴ U	²³⁵ U	²¹⁰ Po	²³⁴ Th	²²⁶ Ra	²¹⁰ Pb	²²⁸ Th	²²⁴ Ra	⁴⁰ K
²³⁸ U	1.00	<i>0.00*</i>	<i>0.29</i>	<i>0.95</i>	<i>0.00</i>	<i>0.47</i>	<i>0.15</i>	<i>0.59</i>	<i>0.45</i>	<i>0.06</i>
²³⁴ U	0.88	1.00	<i>0.05</i>	<i>0.76</i>	<i>0.00</i>	<i>0.17</i>	<i>0.03</i>	<i>0.34</i>	<i>0.36</i>	<i>0.15</i>
²³⁵ U	0.26	0.46	1.00	<i>0.62</i>	<i>0.08</i>	<i>0.15</i>	<i>0.06</i>	<i>0.08</i>	<i>0.72</i>	<i>0.58</i>
²¹⁰ Po	0.01	-0.08	-0.12	1.00	<i>0.63</i>	<i>0.20</i>	<i>0.00</i>	<i>0.73</i>	<i>0.01</i>	<i>0.03</i>
²³⁴ Th	-0.72	-0.71	-0.42	-0.12	1.00	<i>0.26</i>	<i>0.11</i>	<i>0.28</i>	<i>0.78</i>	<i>0.19</i>
²²⁶ Ra	-0.18	-0.33	-0.34	0.31	0.27	1.00	<i>0.01</i>	<i>0.03</i>	<i>0.43</i>	<i>0.23</i>
²¹⁰ Pb	-0.35	-0.49	-0.44	0.74	0.38	0.56	1.00	<i>0.09</i>	<i>0.01</i>	<i>0.05</i>
²²⁸ Th	-0.13	-0.23	-0.41	-0.09	0.26	0.50	0.40	1.00	<i>0.22</i>	<i>0.33</i>
²²⁴ Ra	-0.20	-0.24	-0.10	0.60	0.08	0.21	0.65	0.33	1.00	<i>0.10</i>
⁴⁰ K	-0.44	-0.34	-0.14	-0.50	0.32	-0.29	-0.46	0.24	-0.43	1.00

* p-value = 0.00 corresponds to $p < 0.005$ (strong correlation)

Table 6

Factor loadings of radiological variables on four significant principal components for algae samples. Percentage of variance explained by each principal component and their cumulative percentage of total variance are also given.

Variables	PC1	PC2	PC3	PC4
²³⁸ U	0.55	0.09	-0.16	0.37
²³⁴ U	0.55	-0.01	-0.14	0.42
²¹⁰ Po	-0.05	0.61	0.55	0.36
²³⁴ Th	-0.50	-0.07	-0.57	0.58
²¹⁰ Pb	-0.30	0.56	-0.10	0.07
⁴⁰ K	-0.22	-0.54	0.57	0.46
% of Variance	48.7	35.8	8.1	4.4
Cumulative %	48.7	84.5	92.6	97.0

Table 7Annual effective dose per adult consumer by ingestion of radionuclides from seaweed ($\mu\text{Sv/y}$).

Radionuclide	Green		Brown			Red
	GC	BL	BS	BD	BMean	RH
^{238}U	1.84±0.15	0.98±0.09	0.52±0.06	1.82±0.19	1.03±0.11	1.62±0.14
^{234}U	2.7±0.2	1.22±0.11	0.74±0.07	2.5±0.2	1.37±0.13	2.12±0.18
^{210}Po	160±8	276±8	77±3	265±15	219±8	262±8
^{226}Ra	5±1	8.2±1	4.7±0.8	11.7±1.1	7.9±0.9	15.2±1.2
^{210}Pb	23±8	91±10	23±6	63±10	65±9	130±14
^{228}Th	1.32±0.18	1.78±0.18	1.34±0.14	2.8±0.2	1.9±0.17	4±0.3
^{40}K	11±0.5	7.9±0.4	17.7±0.8	19.3±0.9	14±0.7	6.4±0.4
Total (93d delay)	205±11	388±13	126±7	366±18	310±12	423±16
Total (7d delay)	312±15	574±17	180±7	540±30	458±17	605±19